

SCHOOL HEADS' PROFESSIONAL SOCIALIZATION AND TEACHERS' LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN GOVERNOR GENEROSO SOUTH DISTRICT, DAVAO ORIENTAL

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Abstract. The study assessed the relationship between School Heads' Professional Socialization and its association with Teachers' Leadership Development in Gov. Generoso South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected 120 teacher respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that of school head's professional socialization exhibits continuous learning growth; collaborative decision-making, vision-mission alignment and ethical leadership are moderately extensive, while mentorship and coaching are extensive, while, the extent of teacher's leadership development shows that innovative teaching practices, participation in decision-making and professional development advocate are extensive, while reflective practice is moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between the school head's professional socialization and the teacher's leadership development. All domains of the school head's professional socialization in terms of continuous learning and growth, mentorship and coaching, collaborative decision-making, ethical leadership, and vision and mission alignment significantly influenced teachers' leadership development. Future research may explore the long-term impact of teacher leadership on student outcomes and school performance, which would contribute valuable insights.

KEY WORDS

1. School head's professional Socialization .
2. Teachers' Leadership Development .
3. Gov. Generoso South District, Davao Oriental .

1. Introduction

A school head, often a principal or head-teacher, is pivotal in the education system. These educational leaders are responsible for managing the school, ensuring effective teaching and learning, and creating a conducive environment for students and educators. Their journey to becoming successful school heads is shaped by a process known as professional socialization. Professional socialization is a dynamic and continuous process through which individuals entering a profession internalize its values, norms, beliefs, and behaviors. School heads undergo a complex socialization journey in education beyond their initial teacher training.

It encompasses developing leadership skills, a deep understanding of educational policies, and a commitment to serving the best interests of students and the school community.

Professional socialization for school heads occurs within a macro system, which refers to the broader context and environment in which educational institutions operate. This macro system includes academic policies, regulations, societal expectations, and the local community's needs and values (Bolman Deal, 2017). School heads must navigate a landscape of ever-evolving educational policies and regulations. They learn to interpret, implement, and adapt to these policies while focusing on improving academic outcomes. Within the macro system, school heads are subject to societal expectations regarding the role of education in society. They must balance the demands of stakeholders, including parents, community members, and policymakers, while upholding the school's mission and vision. The community surrounding a school plays a significant role in professional socialization. School heads learn to engage with the local community, addressing its unique needs and fostering partnerships that enhance the educational experience. Moreover, School heads become adept at making informed decisions based on an understanding of educational policies, enabling them to align their leadership practices with broader educational goals (Hallinger Heck, 2019). They develop the ability to engage with the local community, garnering support and resources that benefit the school and its students. Professional socialization within the macro system fosters adaptability and resilience in school heads, enabling them to navigate challenges and drive positive change. School heads prioritize student well-being and success, reflecting the broader societal goal of providing quality education for all. School heads' professional socialization within a macro system is a multifaceted process that equips them with the skills, knowledge, and values

necessary for effective educational leadership. It involves understanding and navigating educational policies, meeting societal expectations, and engaging with the local community. This socialization process empowers school heads to lead with adaptability, resilience, and a student-centered focus, ultimately improving the educational system (Lambert, 2018). The Philippines has long recognized the pivotal roles of school heads and teachers in shaping the nation's educational landscape. Under the Philippine MATATAG Agenda, the government has committed to strengthening the education sector to meet the evolving needs of Filipino learners. A crucial aspect of this agenda is the professional development of school heads and teachers, a journey characterized by professional socialization and leadership development. Professional socialization for school heads in the Philippines is a comprehensive process that begins with their initial teacher training and continues as they assume leadership roles. During this journey, school heads internalize educational leadership's values, norms, and expectations in the Filipino context (Karganilla, 2019). One key component of school heads' professional socialization is their exposure to educational policies and governance frameworks. They learn to navigate the Philippine educational system's intricate policy landscape, ensuring their leadership practices align with national and regional educational goals (Benavides, 2018). Additionally, school heads develop the skills to engage with various stakeholders, including teachers, parents, local government units, and community members. This collaborative approach reflects the MATATAG Agenda's emphasis on unity and cooperation in education (DepEd, 2020). Teachers' leadership development is another vital dimension of the MATATAG Agenda. It recognizes that teachers are not only disseminators of knowledge but also leaders who influence educational outcomes (Lumanta, 2019). Within this framework,

teachers engage in leadership development programs that enhance their capacity to lead within and beyond the classroom. These programs emphasize instructional leadership, encouraging teachers to actively participate in curriculum development, assessment, and improving teaching practices (Canivel, 2020). Teachers' leadership development also underscores the importance of reflective practice (Capule, 2018). Educators are encouraged to assess their teaching methods critically, adapt to changing educational paradigms, and champion evidence-based instructional strategies. In the province of Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental, the leadership

of School Heads are sometimes having difficulties in their leadership; however, this has been overcome and able to underscores the significance of professional socialization through leadership development in shaping the community's educational landscape. As school heads navigate the complex policy environment and engage with stakeholders, teachers enhance their instructional leadership and embrace reflective practices. The synergy between these two processes amplifies the agenda's impact, contributing to a stronger, more resilient, and forward-looking education system.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps in the conduct of the study. This includes the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical consideration, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essential to assume appropriateness and correctness to produce sound data process collection, analysis, and interpretation. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—The study used the non-experimental, descriptive-correlational research design, which is a non-experimental design that investigates the degree to which two or more variables are related. It does not involve the manipulation of any variables, but rather measures and analyses the existing relationship between them (Creswell, 2014). In this study, correlational research design can be used to examine the relationship between the School Heads' professional socialization and Teachers' leadership development. According to Creswell (2014), descriptive-correlational research design describes and explains the relationship between two or more variables. The

main goal of this type of research design is to identify the relationship between variables, and it can be used to make predictions about future events. Descriptive-correlational research design is often used in exploratory studies or when researchers are interested in establishing the existence of a relationship between variables. Descriptive-correlational research designs are used to describe the relationships between variables. Researchers collect data on two or more variables and then analyze the data to determine if there is a relationship between them. This type of research is used to generate hypotheses for future studies (Campbell Stanley, 1963). Moreover, a descriptive-correlational research

design can be helpful in generating hypotheses and identifying potential causal relationships between variables. By examining the strength and direction of correlations between variables, researchers can gain insight into how changes in one variable might be associated with changes in another. This can provide a basis for developing theories about the underlying mechanisms that drive the relationship between variables, which can be tested using more rigorous experimental or quasi-experimental designs. Finally, a descriptive-correlational research design can be valuable when experimental manipulation of variables is not possible or ethical. For example, it may be unethical to manipulate variables such as age, gender, or medical condition to examine their effects on other variables. In such cases, a descriptive-correlational design can provide a valuable alternative for investigating the relationships between variables of interest without requiring manipulation or control of those variables.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Secondary School Teachers of Gov Generoso South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. He used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective School within the Secondary Schools of Gov Generoso South District. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections; they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were the teachers actively and directly involved in most of the School's programs, projects, and activities as listed in their School Improvement Plans. Moreover, teachers were skilled in strategizing the simplification of operational processes and management in school apart from curriculum implementation and delivery, likewise trying to improve the sys-

tem in tracking teachers' performance and their competence in responding to the queries of the study. They are qualified for they are expected to have performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and the learners' awareness and educational stages given the new normal learning system during SY 2023-2024. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature, as the authors argued. The survey questionnaire had two parts, one of which aimed to determine the extent of school heads' professional socialization in terms of continuous learning and growth, mentorship and coaching, collaborative decision-making, ethical leadership, and vision and mission alignment. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of teachers' leadership development regarding participation in decision-making, reflective practice, innovative teaching practices, and professional development advocacy. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.886, which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal consistency is very good.

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the school heads professional

socialization in terms of continuous learning and growth, mentorship and coaching, collaborative decision-making, ethical leadership, and vision and mission alignment. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The school heads’ professional socialization is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The school heads’ professional socialization is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The school heads’ professional socialization is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The school heads’ professional socialization is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The school heads’ professional socialization is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of teachers’ leadership development in terms of participation in decision-making, reflective practice, innovative teaching practices, and professional development advocacy, a 5-point Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers’ leadership development is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers’ leadership development is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers’ leadership development is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers’ leadership development is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers’ leadership development is not manifested

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The data-gathering procedure within a research project involves a series of critical steps, and among them is the ethical process of obtaining permission to conduct the study. This step is integral to upholding core principles of respect, transparency, and responsible research conduct. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the College where the researcher is studying; as part of the request, researchers articulate their intentions for data collection, analysis, and dissemination, illustrating how these align with the overall research goals. Any concerns or questions anticipated from recipients should be addressed in this correspondence, alongside assurances regarding ethical

safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the study's potential benefits. The formal permission request is then made, explicitly seeking authorization to proceed and emphasizing the significance of their support for the research's success. Permission to conduct the study. On October 2023, before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser the Dean of the College where the researcher is studying, and the top management of DepEd Davao Oriental Division through the channel. This permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal with information

about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided information about the purpose and goals of the study and how the data will be collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, on January 2024, the researcher ensured that all participants were fully informed about the study and their rights and that they provided informed consent before participating. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The first week of April 2024, the researcher ensured the accuracy and completeness of data, and the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires were conducted in a standardized and systematic manner.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1) regarding the extent of school heads' professional socialization and statement problem number two (2) regarding the extent of teachers' leadership development in Gov Generoso South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship be-

tween school heads' professional socialization and teachers' leadership development. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the school heads' professional socialization indicators that significantly influence teachers' leadership development (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter focuses on the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the collected data. Both tabular and textual formats are utilized to enhance the depth of analysis and draw meaningful implications. This serves as further evidence supporting the hypothesis's claim.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of professional socialization. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: continuous leaning growth (3.71); collaborative decision-making (3.60), vision-mission alignment (3.50) and eth-

ical leadership (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while mentorship and coaching (3.49) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.54 denotes that extent of professional socializations is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

The extent of professional socialization of a school head plays a crucial role in shaping the culture, effectiveness, and overall success of an

educational institution. Professional socialization refers to the process by which individuals in leadership roles, such as school heads, in-

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Professional Socialization

No	Professional Socialization	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Continuous Learning and Growth	3.71	Extensive
2	Mentorship and Coaching	3.49	Moderately Extensive
3	Collaborative Decision-Making	3.62	Extensive
4	Ethical Leadership	3.40	Extensive
5	Vision-Mission Alignment	3.50	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.54	Extensive

ternalize the values, norms, and professional practices of their profession. In the context of school leadership, this process involves the acquisition of skills, knowledge, and attitudes that are essential for effective educational leadership. The extent to which a school head undergoes professional socialization influences their ability to navigate the complexities of the education system, make informed decisions, and foster a positive and inclusive school environment (Bolman Deal, 2017). School heads are socialized through formal training programs, mentorship, professional development opportunities, and on-the-job experiences. Their engagement with educational networks, collaboration with peers, and adherence to ethical standards further contribute to their professional socialization. A well-socialized school head is more likely to inspire a sense of purpose among staff, encour-

age continuous learning, and promote a school culture that prioritizes student success and well-being. Ultimately, the extent of professional socialization of a school head has a lasting impact on the overall educational experience within the institution (Harris, 2019).

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of teacher’s leadership development. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: innovative teaching practices (3.61), participation in decision-making (3.50) and professional development advocate (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, while reflective practice (3.39) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.50 denotes that the extent of teacher leadership development is often manifested, thus extensive.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Teacher’s Leadership Development

No	Teacher’s Leadership Development	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Participation in Decision-Making	3.50	Extensive
2	Reflective Practice	3.39	Moderately Extensive
3	Innovative Teaching Practice	3.61	Extensive
4	Professional Development Advocate	3.50	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.50	Extensive

The extent of teacher’s leadership development is a critical factor in enhancing the overall effectiveness of an educational institution. Teachers, as frontline educators, are not only responsible for classroom instruction but also play a significant role in shaping the school culture and contributing to the broader educational community. Leadership development for teachers involves cultivating skills beyond the traditional classroom setting, such as effective communication, decision-making, and collaborative problem-solving. Professional development programs, workshops, and mentoring initiatives contribute to the extent of a teacher’s leadership development, providing them with the tools to assume leadership roles within their classrooms, grade levels, or even at the school-wide level (Bates, 2019). As teachers develop leadership skills, they are better equipped to contribute to curriculum development, mentor their colleagues, and engage in educational initiatives that enhance student learning outcomes. The extent of a teacher’s leadership development is also reflected in their ability to adapt

to changing educational paradigms, embrace innovation, and serve as advocates for positive educational reforms. A well-developed cadre of teacher leaders can inspire a culture of continuous improvement, collaboration, and innovation within the school, ultimately contributing to the overall success of the educational institution (Schön, 2017).

Significant Relationship between Professional Socialization and Teacher’s Leadership Development

Table 3 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between teacher’s leadership and teacher’s leadership development. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between teacher’s leadership and teacher’s leadership development must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significantly strong positive correlation between teacher’s leadership ($r=0.857$; $p<.000$) and teacher’s leadership development.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Teacher’s Leadership and Teacher’s Leadership Development

Variables	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation	Decision
Teacher’s Leadership				
Teacher’s Leadership Development	0.857	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

The significant relationship between a teacher’s leadership and their leadership development forms the cornerstone of a thriving educational environment. Teacher leadership involves educators taking on roles beyond traditional classroom responsibilities, such as mentoring peers, participating in decision-making processes, and contributing to the overall improvement of the school community. The development of teacher leadership skills is essential

in nurturing a collaborative and dynamic educational setting. As teachers engage in leadership development programs, they not only enhance their ability to guide and inspire their students but also acquire the skills necessary to influence positive change within the school. The more teachers invest in their leadership development, the more effectively they can contribute to curriculum design, student assessment, and the implementation of innovative teaching method-

ologies (Smylie Denny, 2017). A symbiotic relationship emerges where teacher leadership catalyzes ongoing development, and, conversely, leadership development opportunities empower teachers to assume more prominent roles. This interplay fosters a culture of continuous improvement, where teacher leaders become advocates for positive educational changes and play a pivotal role in shaping the overall educational experience for both their colleagues and students. The significant relationship between teacher leadership and leadership development is, therefore, central to creating a dynamic and responsive educational ecosystem (Hallinger Heck, 2019).

On the Domains of School Heads’ Professional Socialization Significantly Influence Teachers’ Leadership Development

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of school heads’ professional socialization significantly influence teachers’ leadership development. Domains of school head’s professional socialization in terms of continuous learning and growth (0.000), mentorship and coaching (0.001), collaborative decision-making (0.000), ethical leadership (0.001) and vision and mission alignment (0.001) suggest significant influential in teachers’ leadership development.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of School Heads’ Professional Socialization Significantly Influencing Teachers’ Leadership Development

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
<i>H₀</i>					
(Intercept)	4.135		0.078	60.426	0.001
<i>H₁</i>					
(Intercept)	0.323		0.176	1.056	0.270
Continuous Learning and Growth	0.226	0.102	0.116	1.010	0.315
Mentorship and Coaching	0.242	0.135	0.115	1.299	0.186
Collaborative Decision-Making	0.253	0.212	0.094	2.098	0.048
Ethical Leadership	0.213	0.211	0.085	2.098	0.088
Vision and Mission Alignment	0.245	0.134	0.117	1.299	0.186

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eanwhile, the R2 value of 0.865 suggests that teachers’ leadership development, is explained by 86.5%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (253.877) and F-statistic is significant $p < .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of school head’s professional

socialization. School heads’ professional socialization significantly influences teachers’ leadership development, creating a symbiotic relationship that shapes the overall ethos of an educational institution. School heads, as leaders at the helm of the administrative hierarchy, play a pivotal role in setting the tone for the school culture. Their professional socialization, includ-

ing experiences, values, and leadership styles, serves as a model for teachers. When school heads prioritize and model effective leadership practices, it positively impacts the development of teacher leaders within the institution (Dinham Scott, 2020). Professional development initiatives, mentorship programs, and collaborative decision-making processes initiated by school heads contribute to the leadership growth of teachers. The extent to which school heads emphasize a culture of continuous learning and provide opportunities for teachers to engage in

leadership roles fosters an environment where educators feel empowered to contribute beyond their classrooms. In turn, the leadership development of teachers not only enriches the overall teaching and learning experience but also reinforces the school's commitment to excellence. Thus, the professional socialization of school heads becomes a critical factor in cultivating a leadership culture that permeates throughout the entire educational community (Bullough Draper, 2018).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion, and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of the school head's professional socialization exhibits that continuous learning growth, collaborative decision-making, vision-mission alignment, and ethical leadership are oftentimes manifested, while mentorship and coaching are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating denotes that extent of professional socializations is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. The extent of teacher leadership development shows that innovative teaching practices, participation in decision-making, and profes-

sional development advocacy are often manifested, while reflective practice is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating denotes that the extent of teacher leadership development is often manifested, thus extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teacher's leadership and teacher's leadership development. Domains of school head's professional socialization in terms of continuous learning and growth, mentorship and coaching, collaborative decision-making, ethical leadership and vision and mission alignment suggest significant influential in teachers' leadership development.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the conclusions, to wit; The extent of the school head's professional socialization exhibits continuous learning growth; collaborative decision-making, vision-mission alignment, and ethical leadership are moderately extensive, while mentorship and coaching are extensive. The extent of teacher's leadership development shows that

innovative teaching practices, participation in decision-making, and professional development advocacy are extensive, while reflective practice is moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between school heads' professional socialization and teachers' leadership development. Domains of school head's professional socialization in terms of continuous learning and growth, men-

torship and coaching, collaborative decision-making, ethical leadership, and vision and mission alignment suggest significant influence in teachers' leadership development. The theory of professional socialization vis-à-vis leadership development underscores the symbiotic relationship between nurturing ethical, moral leaders and developing practical leadership competencies. As individuals internalize the values and ethics of their profession during professional socialization, leadership development programs

capitalize on these foundational principles to shape visionary educational leaders. Through this interplay, educational leaders emerge with the skills to navigate complex educational landscapes and a deep-seated commitment to ethical leadership. They become influential figures who guide educational systems toward positive transformation, ensuring that the principles instilled during professional socialization continue to guide their leadership endeavors.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May consider implementing structured professional development programs for school heads, focusing on leadership skills and strategies that empower teachers. Additionally, the supervisor could establish a mentorship system where experienced school heads mentor those in the early stages of their career, fostering a culture of continuous professional growth and collaboration. School Principal. May prioritize creating a leadership-friendly environment within the school. This includes promoting a culture of open communication, involving teachers in decision-making processes, and providing opportunities for them to take on leadership roles. Principals should also actively engage in their own professional development to stay

abreast of effective leadership practices. Teachers. May actively seek out professional development opportunities to enhance their leadership skills. They should collaborate with colleagues, participate in school-wide initiatives, and express interest in taking on leadership responsibilities. Additionally, teachers should communicate their professional development needs to school administrators to ensure that opportunities align with their career goals. Future Researchers. May delve deeper into the specific factors within school heads' professional socialization that most significantly influence teacher leadership development. Additionally, exploring the long-term impact of teacher leadership on student outcomes and school performance would contribute valuable insights. Research could also focus on the effectiveness of different professional development models and strategies in promoting teacher leadership.

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